

Creation of open educational resources (OER) and digital and media competences of future teachers

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Abstract

The digital and media competencies of future teachers are foundational for driving positive change in education. Recognizing this, and addressing the gaps in new media proficiency among pre-service teachers, a pedagogical experiment was designed to enhance their creative use of new technologies. In the 2023/2024 academic year, a new initiative was introduced at Jagiellonian University, Poland, aimed at improving pre-service teachers' knowledge and skills in creating open educational resources (OER). Leveraging the theoretical and diagnostic framework of the international REMEDIS project, a series of activities were conducted over multiple sessions, enabling pre-service teachers to develop their own original OER using video tutorials. Quantitative research conducted during this experiment revealed the following insights: 1) The proposed training model has significantly enhanced teachers' digital competence and shows promise for long-term implementation; 2) However, one area needing improvement is the dissemination of OER (e.g., via YouTube). While YouTube is widely used, this does not necessarily mean that all participants are proficient in uploading videos to popular platforms; 3) As age increases, there is a noticeable decline in digital competence among teachers in certain areas; 4) An effective training program should have highly focused learning objectives related to the essential skills for creating, editing, and sharing OER; 5) Overloading the program with additional digital and media skills does not effectively improve teachers' competence in OER creation.

Keywords: OER, digital and media literacy, videotutorials, future teachers, Poland

Introduction

Digital and media competencies are now essential resources for effective teaching, particularly in the creation of contemporary educational materials that support both teaching and learning processes. As a result, recent pedagogical literature has increasingly focused on the digital competencies of both current and future teachers (Palacios Rodríguez et al., 2023; Nguyen & Habók, 2024; Tomczyk & Fedeli, 2022; Tomczyk & Fedeli, 2021). Analyses to date reveal a wide range of digital competence models and varying attitudes toward ICT within this group (Tomczyk et al., 2024). The data collected identifies several challenges faced by institutions responsible for training future educators.

First, although young people are prolific users of digital resources, their activities are largely confined to basic communication, information retrieval, and entertainment. Their digital competencies are often limited to the effective consumption of digital information. Second, this limited level of digital and media competence hinders the development of broader teaching-related digital skills, which require more than just content consumption. Teachers must be able to create valuable educational materials. Third, teacher training programs must integrate trends and developments highlighted by media pedagogy experts (Tatnall & Fluck, 2022; Ozyurt & Ozyurt, 2024; Tonbuloğlu & Tonbuloğlu, 2023; Zou et al., 2022), such as the potential of multimedia delivery, the constructive use of new e-services for visual presentation, the increased frequency and effectiveness of e-learning and its derivatives, and the expanded use of edtech in its broadest sense.

Combining the opportunities offered by edtech with the limitations in how future teachers currently engage with new media presents a series of challenges. Among these, the ability to create open digital resources (OER) that serve as effective teaching tools across various contexts and stages of education is especially critical. For instance, OER in the form of video tutorials allows students to learn at their own pace, with the ability to pause, rewind, or replay content, thus enhancing learning outcomes. Video tutorials are particularly beneficial for complex material that requires repeated review. Such OER solutions are versatile and can be applied at nearly any educational level. However, creating these digital teaching resources necessitates specific digital and media skills, including proficiency in edtech tools for OER creation, camera and microphone operation, and video editing. Beyond technical skills, educators must be able to adapt their narrative style to the content and efficiently share multimedia OER. Research on OER and the digital competence of current and future teachers underscores that video tutorials can play a pivotal role in modern education, promoting learner autonomy and supporting flexible teaching and learning processes. However, their effective creation requires well-designed training that equips teachers to leverage the full potential of these sophisticated teaching tools (Tomczyk et al., 2023b).

Creating OER in the form of video tutorials offers significant benefits for the professional preparation of future teachers. Through hands-on workshops in computer labs, students learn how to record screenshots, use their own image and voice, edit multimedia materials, and share OER on platforms like YouTube (Guillén-Gámez et al., 2024; Tomczyk,

2023c; Basgal et al., 2023). Such classes not only elevate basic digital and media competencies but also enhance teachers' professional edtech skills (Skantz-Åberg et al., 2022).

Given the rapid evolution of e-services, improving the digital and media competencies of both current and future teachers is crucial for sustaining an information society and meeting the demands of modern education. Systematic analyses of ICT-based innovations and educational programs for teachers reveal a consistent need—across all geographic and cultural contexts—to strengthen digital and media competencies among educators (Vissenberg et al., 2023). However, the support provided must meet certain criteria, as outlined by international initiatives like the REMEDIS project (Rethinking Media Literacy and Digital Skills in Europe) (Martinez et al., 2023; d'Haenens et al., 2024). Using the REMEDIS framework, this article presents a case study and research findings on building teacher skills in line with current trends in media pedagogy.

Research methodology

The primary objective of this research was to conduct an intervention aimed at enhancing the digital competencies of future teachers, particularly in the development of open educational resources (OER). Additionally, the intervention sought to refine the educational program for digital competence development by validating the author's educational model. This initiative was also aligned with the international REMEDIS project, co-financed by the National Science Centre (NCN, Poland).

The project activities were designed to shift pedagogical students from passive media consumption to active and creative use of ICT. This transformation was

expected to significantly boost teachers' ability to develop modern, cost-effective educational solutions based on ICT. The intervention was designed with several anticipated benefits in mind:

1. Enhancement of teachers' digital and media competencies,
2. Strengthening of their ability to integrate new media into education,
3. Development of skills to create modern ICT-based educational solutions,
4. Improvement in the quality of teacher education, aligning it with current information society trends, and
5. Upgrading of ICT courses at Jagiellonian University (Martinez et al., 2024).

These activities were implemented through the collaboration of multiple institutions committed to improving the quality of education. A central role in this project was played by the Institute of Pedagogy at Jagiellonian University (UJ), where the pedagogical innovation was introduced during the 2023/2024 academic year. The UJ's involvement was strategic, given the access to a research group consisting of both future and current teachers. The project also received significant methodological support from the Polish Society for Educational Technology and Media, a non-governmental organization comprising experts in educational digitization (Martinez et al., 2024).

Data collection for evaluating the innovation was conducted from October 2023 to June 2024 using an online survey (MS Forms). The survey instrument included both a pre-test and a post-test, employing a triangulated approach:

A tool mapping new media usage styles (Martinez et al., 2024). The tool contained 12 statements related to the following areas of ICT use: I know how to secure my device (e.g. PIN, screen pattern, fingerprint, facial recognition) ; I know how to store photos, documents or other files in the cloud (e.g. Google Drive,

iCloud) I know how to use private browsing (e.g. incognito mode) ; I know how to use advanced search features on search engines ; I know how to check if information I find on the Internet is correct ; I know how to check if a website is trustworthy ; Depending on the situation, I know which medium or tool to use to communicate with someone (e.g. phone call, WhatsApp message, email) ; I know which pictures and information about me I can share online make a phone call, send a WhatsApp message, send an email) ; I know which pictures and information about me I can share online ; I know when it is appropriate and when it is not appropriate to use emoticons (e.g. emoticons), text (e.g. LOL, OMG) and capital letters ; I know how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g. pictures, music, video, GIFs) ; I know how to edit existing digital images, music and videos; I know how to make sure that many people see what I post online. Each respondent referred to knowledge on a 5 degree likert scale ranging from 1- totally untrue in my case to 5 - very true in my case. The internal consistency of the tool was 0.911.

A proprietary tool measuring skills related to creating video tutorials (Tomczyk et al., 2023b). The tool consisted of 5 areas necessary to create effective OER and included the following statements: I can take a screenshot as a video; I can create digital video tutorials; I can explain the use of an office suite (e.g. word, excel, power point) to others; I know how to upload a high volume video using the internet; I can upload a video to YouTube or a related website. Responses to the areas indicated were placed on a scale from 1-very disagree to very agree. The internal consistency of the tool was 0.834.

The innovation involved 103 participants for the pre-test and 82 for the post-test, with the cohort consisting of 102 females and 1 male. Among them, 44% held a master's or doctoral degree. Participants were born between 1996 and 2003, with an average age of 35 years (standard deviation: 5.04 years). Of the respondents, 59% were full-time

students, 25% were employed full-time, and 8% were working part-time.

The course aimed at developing OER creation skills and was structured in three stages (Martinez et al., 2024):

1. Introduction to ICT: Focused on the basics of digital data management and the use of office software according to the ECDL standard. Some participants, particularly those in professional training, were introduced to data processing using AI tools.
2. Using and Creating OER: Training was provided by a media pedagogy specialist on using free software for creating and sharing OER. Participants were supported by YouTube tutorials to help them create their own OER.
3. Distribution: The OER created by participants were shared, allowing for quality control of the learning resources developed. It was anticipated that these materials would be used by other students for self-study in future editions of courses like "Introduction to Information Technology" or "Media in Education."

The general training framework is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Intervention structure.

To structure the collected data, the following research questions were posed:

1. What is the baseline level of digital and media skills for creating OER in the form of video tutorials?
2. What is the level of digital and media literacy in creating OER in the form of video tutorials after training?
3. To what extent do age influence OER creation skills?
4. To what extent do the skills of creating video tutorials co-occur?
5. Which factors related to new media usage styles impact the improvement of digital and media competencies associated with OER creation?

Results

The table provides descriptive statistics for five digital competencies measured before and after a training intervention. Notably, all mean scores increased from the pre-test to the post-test, indicating an overall improvement in the participants' digital skills. The largest increase in mean score is seen in the ability to create digital video tutorials, rising from 2.870 to 4.071, suggesting significant progress in this area. Similarly, the skill of uploading high-volume videos also saw substantial improvement, with the mean score increasing from 3.046 to 4.095.

Despite these gains, the standard deviations remain relatively consistent across both tests. Skewness values reveal a shift towards more positive self-assessment post-training, particularly in creating digital video tutorials and uploading videos, where negative

skewness increased, indicating more participants rated themselves highly.

The percentages of participants who found the statements "completely untrue" or "rather untrue" for their case decreased notably in the post-test, further reflecting the effectiveness of the training. For example, in the pre-test, 29.63% of participants rated their ability to create digital video tutorials as "rather untrue," but this dropped to just 1.19% in the post-test. The "very true" responses increased in all categories, most significantly in the ability to create digital video tutorials and upload videos, highlighting substantial skill development. "Taking a screenshot as a video" (0.36) and "Uploading a video to YouTube or a related website" (0.32) have small effect sizes. This indicates a modest improvement in these areas after the training. "Explaining the use of an office suite" (0.45) falls on the borderline between small and medium. The improvement here is moderate, suggesting that the training had a noticeable but not large impact on this skill. "Creating digital video tutorials" (1.08) and "Uploading a high-volume video using the internet" (0.93) have large effect sizes, indicating significant improvement. Overall, the training program appears to have effectively enhanced participants' digital competencies across all measured areas. Details of the descriptive statistics are provided in Table 1 and Figure 2.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for pre-test and post-test

	I can take a screenshot as a video		I can create digital video tutorials		I can explain the use of an office suite		I know how to upload a high volume video using the internet		I can upload a video to YouTube or a related website	
	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test
Mean	3.546	3.988	2.870	4.071	3.398	3.881	3.046	4.095	3.250	3.631
Std. Deviation	1.218	1.227	1.095	1.128	1.058	1.080	1.097	1.147	1.169	1.230
Skewness	-0.426	-1.379	0.088	-1.640	-0.522	-1.286	-0.050	-1.760	-0.109	-0.848

Kurtosis	-0.870	1.041	-0.749	2.278	-0.127	1.489	-0.652	2.586	-0.884	-0.190
Completely untrue in my case	5.556	9.524	10.185	8.333	6.481	7.143	8.333	9.524	6.481	9.524
Rather untrue in my case	17.593	3.571	29.630	1.190	11.111	2.381	23.148	3.571	22.222	9.524
Sometimes true, sometimes false	20.370	7.143	29.630	5.952	31.481	14.286	33.333	0	27.778	14.286
Rather true in my case	29.630	38.095	24.074	44.048	37.963	47.619	25.926	45.238	26.852	41.667
Very true in my case	26.852	41.667	6.481	40.476	12.963	28.571	9.259	41.667	16.667	25.000

Figure 2. Pre-test and post-test results assessing the level of digital and media competence in the creation of video tutorials.

A detailed analysis of the data revealed

that in three instances, age was associated with teacher digital competence. Specifically, as age increases, the ability to create OER tends to decline. This correlation is particularly noticeable in skills such as creating video screenshots ($r=0.388$, $p<0.005$), producing digital educational video

tutorials ($r=0.208$, $p<0.05$), and sharing content on YouTube ($r=0.302$, $p<0.005$). However, it's important to note that while these correlations are statistically significant, they do not reach the threshold for being considered moderate or strong. The varying levels of correlation, as determined by the

Spearman coefficient, are illustrated below.

Figure 3. Pre-test and post-test results assessing the level of digital and media competence in the creation of video tutorials.

When addressing question 4, data from the post-test tool was analyzed. Spearman's correlations revealed a moderate to strong relationship between the various aspects of digital competence. This suggests that proficiency in one area, such as taking screenshots, tends to be associated with proficiency in other essential skills, like creating and uploading videos. However, the correlation between sharing videos on YouTube and other digital competencies was only moderate. This might be because this specific skill was not sufficiently covered in the training program, and also because using YouTube is commonly associated with consuming content rather than sharing one's own.

Table 2. Co-occurrence of digital competences for creating and sharing OER

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. I can take a screenshot as a video	—			
2. I can create digital video tutorials	0.731 ***	—		
3. I can explain the use of an MS Office or similar	0.618 ***	0.706 ***	—	
4. I know how to upload a high volume video using the internet	0.769 ***	0.852 ***	0.765 ***	—
5. I can upload a video to YouTube or a related website	0.575 ***	0.586 ***	0.532 ***	0.546 ***

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Based on multivariate regression analysis, it was observed that, in most cases, changes in elementary digital and media competencies do not significantly contribute to improving teachers' digital competence in creating and sharing video

tutorials. However, one independent variable in the proposed model, "I know how to edit existing digital images, music, and videos," significantly impacts the three areas related to OER (Open Educational Resources) discussed. This indicates a shared domain between digital competence and the creation of open-access educational materials. Enhancing specific skills related to digital media management emerges as crucial for strengthening teachers' activities using

new media. It's important to note that other elements included in the model are not directly linked to the creation, editing, and sharing of OER, and therefore, do not influence the dependent variables. In practice, this suggests that intervention programs for teachers should offer highly targeted educational content aligned with the specific ICT-related tasks they need to perform.

Table 3. Multivariate regression analysis for five areas of digital competence (dependent variables)

	I can take a screenshot as a video R= ,53787354 R2= ,28930794 F(12,82)=2,78 17 p<,00316			I can create digital video tutorials R= ,56410645 R2= ,31821608 F(12,82)=3,18 94 p<,00089			I can explain the use of an MS Office or simmlar R= ,53690452 R2= ,28826647 F(12,82)=2,76 76 p<,00330			I know how to upload a high volume video using the internet R= ,59284066 R2= ,35146005 F(12,82)=3,70 32 p<,00018			I can upload a video to YouTube or a related website R= ,56054754 R2= ,31421354 F(12,82)=3,13 09 p<,00107		
	β	t	p	β	t	p	β	t	p	β	t	p	β	t	p
Intercept		1.41	0.16		0.18	0.86		0.19	0.85		0.43	0.67		0.47	0.64
I know how to secure my device (e.g. PIN, screen pattern, fingerprint, facial recognition)	0.24	1.72	0.09	0.21	1.53	0.13	0.04	0.32	0.75	0.09	0.70	0.49	0.05	0.38	0.71
I know how to store photos, documents or other files in the cloud (e.g. Google Drive, iCloud)	0.07	0.42	0.67	0.33	2.10	0.04	0.11	0.67	0.50	0.19	1.24	0.22	0.02	0.13	0.90
I know how to use private browsing (e.g. incognito mode)	0.26	2.21	0.03	0.03	0.24	0.81	0.03	0.28	0.78	0.10	0.85	0.40	0.01	0.12	0.91
I know how to use advanced search features on search engines	0.20	1.48	0.14	0.05	0.40	0.69	0.08	0.60	0.55	0.16	1.23	0.22	0.01	0.09	0.93
I know how to check if information I find on the Internet is correct	0.15	0.85	0.40	0.09	0.49	0.63	0.21	1.15	0.25	0.09	0.52	0.61	0.02	0.13	0.89
I know how to check if a website is trustworthy	0.04	0.24	0.81	0.30	1.72	0.09	0.03	0.17	0.86	0.14	0.81	0.42	0.13	0.73	0.47
Depending on the situation, I know which medium or tool to use to communicate with someone (e.g. phone call, WhatsApp message, email)	0.15	0.91	0.36	0.02	0.14	0.89	0.02	0.12	0.90	0.02	0.15	0.88	0.31	1.92	0.06
I know which pictures and information about me I can share online make a phone call, send a WhatsApp	0.34	1.91	0.06	0.03	0.18	0.86	0.21	1.20	0.24	0.18	1.07	0.29	0.49	2.77	0.01

message, send an email)																
I know which pictures and information about me I can share online ;	0.21	1.19	0.24	0.15	0.90	0.37	0.07	0.39	0.70	0.15	0.94	0.35	0.05	0.32	0.75	
I know when it is appropriate and when it is not appropriate to use emoticons (e.g. emoticons), text (e.g. LOL, OMG) and capital letters ; I know how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g. pictures, music, video, GIFs) ;	0.07	0.43	0.67	0.04	0.29	0.78	0.09	0.57	0.57	0.04	0.24	0.81	0.04	0.27	0.79	
I know how to edit existing digital images, music and videos	0.38	2.34	0.02	0.19	1.18	0.24	0.16	0.97	0.34	0.36	2.34	0.02	0.40	2.52	0.01	
I know how to make sure that many people see what I post online	0.16	1.30	0.20	0.32	2.61	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.96	0.07	0.58	0.56	0.05	0.43	0.67	

Discussion and conclusion

The proposed training model has significantly enhanced teachers' digital competencies and is well-suited for long-term implementation, both in introductory ICT courses and specialized academic programs focused on media use in education. Developed based on insights from the international REMEDIS project (d'Haenens et al., 2024), the training program's universal design makes it adaptable for nearly all teacher education institutions. This model is particularly valuable for institutions planning to modify their curricula to reflect a shift in how new media is utilized by teachers. The innovation introduced by this program transforms ICT usage from a passive consumption of educational content to an active creation of valuable digital materials. This approach aligns with global trends in media pedagogy, which emphasize balancing passive and active use of educational technology by teachers (Caena & Redecker, 2019; Instefjord, 2015).

Despite the model's high effectiveness, as evidenced by data from pre-tests and

post-tests, there are areas for improvement, particularly in how teachers engage with new media. For example, the smallest gains were observed in sharing course-generated material on popular platforms such as YouTube. This trend reflects a broader societal pattern, not limited to teachers, where digital content consumption outweighs the creation and sharing of materials. While this is a natural tendency in an information society, it also highlights the low level of skills required to upload videos to such platforms. It is crucial to recognize that using a website involves varying levels of sophistication. The ability to search for and view content does not automatically equate to the ability to post videos (Nikolidakis & Anastasopoulou, 2012; Shoufan & Mohamed, 2022; Fyfield, 2022).

As age increases, a decline in certain areas of teacher digital competence becomes apparent. This relationship is not consistent across all components of digital competence and does not exhibit a strong linear correlation, but it is statistically significant. The extent to which age influences new media usage and digital competence among different groups of teachers (e.g., digital natives versus

digital immigrants) has been a subject of debate in the literature for many years (Napal Fraile et al., 2018; Portillo et al., 2020; Sira et al., 2021). This ongoing discussion is essential for providing appropriate methodological and training support, as well as for designing targeted training programs for specific groups. Furthermore, the moderate correlation levels challenge the stereotype that all teachers classified as digital immigrants inherently possess lower digital and media competence (Sánchez-Cruzado et al., 2021; Rubach & Lazarides, 2021).

Another key insight from the collected data is the importance of aligning training programs with well-defined learning objectives and practical exercises. Such programs should focus on developing skills to create, edit, and share OER using accessible software, while also considering financial constraints. Therefore, it is recommended that similar training programs utilize free software that can be used both in computer labs and on teachers' personal computers (Nazarova et al., 2021; Sattar et al., 2015). The preparation phase of the training should avoid overloading participants with exercises that do not directly support the course objectives, ensuring the program remains systematic and progressively challenging.

In summary, the presented innovation emphasizes the importance of evidence-based solutions with a focus on current trends in media pedagogy. This approach not only enhances teachers' digital competence in a cost-effective manner but also empowers them to creatively harness the potential of cyberspace, thereby improving students' access to educational content. Moreover, this model can be integrated with other educational approaches, such as e-learning, blended learning, and MOOCs, aligning with the

principles of openness and multimedia in educational resources developed through grassroots efforts.

Acknowledgments

This article was written as part of the REMEDIS project, which is supported in Poland by the National Science Centre - NCN [021/03/Y/HS6/00275] under the CHANSE ERA-NET Co-fund, awarded funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme [contract number 101004509].

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